

OUR VISION FOR A EUROPEAN eDNA DIGITAL ECOSYSTEM

Aquatic environmental DNA (eDNA) holds enormous potential for biodiversity research and monitoring, contributing to the development of effective policy and regulatory frameworks. However, this potential has yet to be realised.

eDNAAqua-Plan is developing a roadmap to guide the transition from the current fragmented and sub-optimal digital landscape to a vision of a more harmonised, interoperable, and sustainable ecosystem, based on FAIR data practices. This future landscape will support the implementation of the Marine Strategy Framework Directive, the Water Framework Directive and help us achieve the goals of the EU Mission: Restore our Ocean and Waters, and the EU Green Deal. **Discover and help shape the eDNAAqua-Plan vision.**

The Vision

- Increased adoption of interoperable standards and widely used web-technologies
- Expansion of minimum collected metadata
- A network of connected, searchable and reliable reference libraries
- Federation, not centralisation: Building on what exists
- Better resourced data management
- Quality label for databases and libraries implementing best practices
- Incentivised community participation (acknowledgements and data attributions)
- Local action in a global context

Have your say

Achieving this vision will require community action at all levels: technical, cultural, funding and policy/regulatory. We want to hear from you about the feasibility of implementing our vision. Are you:

- A scientist collecting or analysing eDNA?
- A repository, database or reference library dealing with eDNA data?
- A public body that uses or would like to use eDNA in your monitoring activities?
- A policy-maker interested in the wider use of eDNA in biodiversity monitoring?
- A funding body that supports biodiversity research?
- Generally interested in the workings of eDNA?

ednaquaplan.com/get-involved

Provide your feedback and help shape the future of eDNA biodiversity monitoring

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18 project partners

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Discover the full & detailed eDNA Aqua-Plan at doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16367374

LEGEND

- Collaborations:
- eDNA domain-specific repositories:
- Process-specific repositories:
- Broad-scope repositories:
- Data/Metadata:
- Data formats:
- Workflow steps:
- Analytical steps:
- Tools:
- Main data flows:
- Optional connections:
- Resources are used (arrow points from user):
- Server communication TBD:
- (Meta)data standard:
- Information exchange/exposure: